

The Bloodiest Battle of 1851: Fought Between the Kikrüma Nagas and the British

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Abstract

In the Middle of the 19th century, a very significant and historical battlefield took place in the North Eastern Frontiers Hills (or Naga Hills) between the Britishers and the Kikrüma Nagas. Historically speaking, this was the only battlefield worthy to be mentioned as far as the Britishers adventured to this part of the Naga region. They fought the bloodiest battle ever fought in the entire North-Eastern Frontiers hills on the 11th, February 1851 at Kikrüma. Kikrüma village is situated at the extreme southwest of the present Phek District of Nagaland. They belong to the Chokri-speaking group of the Chakhesang tribe. Kikrüma village on the eve of the Battle of 1851, had more than 1000 households, having more than 2000 warriors. They were dreaded by their neighbouring villages, even the then most powerful Raja Gambhir Singh of Manipur was afraid to take on them. This paper is an attempt to discuss and analyse what factors and circumstances led to the outbreak of the Bloodiest Battle of 1851 at Kikrüma village. At the same time, the paper will also highlight the consequences of this battle in this part of the Naga region.

Keywords: Angami Nagas, Britishers, Khonoma, Kikrüma village, and Naga warriors.

Background of the Battle of 1851:

The frequent raids by the Angami Naga villages in the plains of Dimapur and North Cachar, and in the plains of Assam were a nuisance to the British and an irritant for their trading centres. In response to the frequent raids by the Angami warriors, the British were compelled to give more attention to raids. The forces required were sent from nearby posts like Haflong. (Kikon, 2023) Here it should be noted that the modern Naga history began with the Treaty of Yandaboo on the 24th February, 1826. According to the Treaty of Yandaboo, concluded between the Burmese and the British, the independence of Manipur was acknowledged by both parties, and the king of Burma ceased to have control over the states of Cachar, Jaintia and Assam. In the meantime, the British Government also wished to establish direct communication from Assam to Manipur for easy administration; and this could only be possible by finding out routes via Naga Hills. During this period, Gambhir Singh, the Manipur Raja and Tularam, the Senapati of Cachar, expressed their inability to control the Nagas. Tularam could not undertake any expedition to the Naga Hills owing to stringent resources, though the Manipur Rajah could harass the Nagas, he could

not prevent them from committing raids. The British seized the opportunity and from now on began to explore the hitherto unknown land-the Naga Hills. (Horam, 2016)

The Angami Nagas continued to raid the British territory intermittently. In a treaty executed with Gambhir Singh, the Raja of Manipur in 1833, it was stipulated that “in the event of anything happening on the eastern frontier of the British territories, the Raja will, when required, assist the British Government with a portion of his troops”. According to Edward Gait who served as an Assistant Commissioner of Assam, in his famous book entitled “A History of Assam,” says, “This policy proving a failure, it was abandoned in favour of one of repression by our troops; and between the years 1835 and 1851, ten military expeditions were led to into the hills”. (Gait, 2015)

The first expedition was in January 1839 under the stewardship of Lieutenant Vincent, the British Sub Assistant, to investigate the causes of regular raids by the Angami Nagas in the plain areas of the British territories. However, this expedition was not successful mainly because of the unflinching Naga resistance, and partly because of the mismanagement by the British authorities. (Horam, 2016) The second expedition in 1840 marked the first successful expedition of the colonial power in the Naga Hills. During the second expedition, Lieutenant Vincent made a truce agreement with the Nagas who agreed to pay annual tributes to the British. Lieutenant Vincent submitted a detailed report of his, first and second expeditions and on the whole Angami question. Some Naga villages towards the Manipur border were in dread of the Manipur attack. In his reports, he pointed out that every Angami Village was divided into two parties, one attached to the interest of Manipur and the other to the British, but each only worked for an alliance to get aid in crushing the opposite faction. In his report, Lieutenant Vincent wrote “The attacks on our villages, so far as could be traced, were always made by the Manipuri factions, and never by those who looked to us for alliance. Any English officer entering the hills and taking up his post at a Naga village was looked on merely as the ally of the Teppremah or Assamese faction, and not as the representative of any paramount power. Hence an officer establishing himself should take up an independent post and not locate himself in a Naga village. Besides the ‘grand clans’ in each village, there were indiscriminate burnings of villages should be avoided as injuring friends as well as foes.” (Mackenzie, 2005 & Venuh, 2019)

When in April 1844, Vincent’s Assistant went to collect the first year’s tribute, the Nagas refused to pay any tribute and instead began to commit a series of raids on the neighbouring plains. The British government decided to put an end to this insolence of the Nagas and henceforth intensified both retaliatory and defensive military action. (Horam, 2016)

Of the many clashes that took place in the hills, one village that long proved undefeatable was the Angami Naga village of Khonoma. Its warriors ambushed British forces on multiple occasions and when the British troops advanced, they successfully barricaded themselves behind heavily fortified stockades. Khonomas’s strength and stamina frustrated the British, and soon the leaves of punitive expeditions were

to bring this village down, assuming that if Khonoma surrendered other Naga villages would follow suit. But while Khonoma warriors were hotly pursued, and their village surrounded and attacked, it could not be defeated. However, in the 10th expedition, with a force of 500 soldiers, and even more 'coolies'(partners) under several British officers in 1850, first took up position in Mezoma, a village the British had brought under their control during earlier expeditions, they proceeded towards Khonoma. The British in this 10th expedition could defeat Khonoma warriors by propelling mortar after mortar into the village whilst attacking its stockades. (Allen, 2023 & Wouters, 2015)

Circumstances Leading to the Battle of 1851:

It was sometime in early 1851 (during the tenth expedition) when the Britishers were already there at Mezoma village, defending the Jabeilie clan against Neitholie's clan and already had contacts villages around Mezoma, many became friendly except Khonoma village and Neitholie clan of Mezoma. The news about the intrusion of the British in the internal affairs of the neighbouring villages reached the people of Kikröma and they felt that their authority over the region had been challenged, because, their village was most powerful and dreaded by all around the region, and earlier the village of Khonoma too, fell within the mighty power of Kikröma. Consequently, the people of Kikröma sent a challenge to Captain Reid, stationed at Mezoma, by saying, "Why don't the Sipahees come to fight us?" Curious to know who were these people, on 3rd February 1851, the Britishers under the command of Capt. Reid and Lt. Vincent along with 1st and 2nd Assam Light Infantry proceeded for the first time, with "two 3-pounder guns, two mortars and hundred-armed personnel" to discover the Kikröma village. By then, (1851), Kikröma village had more than 1000 households having more than 2000 warriors, as reported by Lieutenant Vincent. Among those, warriors like Neiho, Müswöri, etc. had the records of having taken more than 70 heads. They were dreaded by their neighbouring villages. (Wouters, 2015 & Venuh, 2019)

On their way, the Britishers came across the villages situated below the foothills of the eastern side of Mt. Japfü, present Southern Angami and faced some minor resistances but eventually subdued them to their side and halted at Pudunamai (Puswumi) village of Mao tribe. When Captain Reid revealed his destination, the dreaded side of the Kikröma Nagas was told to him by the local people. If in pre-colonial days, the village of Khonoma controlled much of the foothills directly adjacent to the Assam plains, and often executed raids on the plains, Kikröma had established itself as a powerhouse deeper inside the hills, closer to the plains of Manipur than to the Brahmaputra Valley. The village's location, perched on a hilltop, while of inconvenience in several ways, had helped the village grow to supremacy; enemies could be spotted from afar while the steep, rocky slope made for a natural defence wall. Its warriors were many and were known and feared widely for their daring, determination, and ferocity. Over the years, they had exerted their control over a large number of villages in its vicinity, extracted tribute from them, and raided and pillaged those reluctant to accept its sway. British officers were aware of Kikröma standing and

strength: "(Kikrüma) was said to contain about 1,000 houses, and having more than 2000 warriors, and they were dreaded by all around as a bloodthirsty people, who think nothing of murder for the sake of plunder: they boasted of having a man in their village who had killed seventy men." They were feared by their neighbouring villages and were considered 'Wild, Bold, Ruthless, and Intelligent'. Even the then, most powerful Raja Gambhir Singh of Manipur, was afraid to take on them. To them, every mountain torrent was a highway, and no forest, however dense, was impassable. (Wouters, 2015 & Venuh, 2019)

At one point, Captain Reid decided not to proceed further under the pretext of difficulty in provisioning the troops and transporting the armour. But on February 5th, 1851, two young men from Kikrüma village brought a challenge from their people, to come to their village and prove who had the greatest power in these hills. Till then, there was no power known to have challenged the superiority of Kikrüma Nagas. The two men, not knowing the firepower of the Britishers, scornfully declared that they did not care for their weapons and said; "Your Sipahes are flesh and blood as well as we are and we will fight with spears and shields and see who are the best men; here is a specimen of our weapon," and handed over a handsome spear to Captain Reid and Lt. Vincent. (Achumi, 2012, Puroh, 2012 & Allen, 2023) B.C. Allen in his reputed book entitled "Gazetteer of Naga Hills and Manipur" writes "The Manipuris, so they said, were afraid to meet them, and they doubted whether the British were of a different temper. It would have been fatal to our slowly developing prestige to decline this challenge, and a move was accordingly made against the village." (Allen, 2023)

The Britishers too seemed afraid to take on them, because that was the first time they had been openly challenged (twice) by a Naga village in their history. However, to save the honour and image of the British Empire and mostly to avoid the injurious effect when returning to Mezoma without accepting the challenge, which would have been attributed to fear, Captain Reid determined at once to uphold the name and honour of his country, decided to accept the challenge; he, therefore told the messengers that "if they wished to fight us, they would soon have the opportunity". Even Lieutenant Vincent accepted the challenge considering the British prestige and the necessity to make the Nagas aware of their power. (Achumi, 2012)

Preparation of the Battle of 1851 by Both Parties:

Captain Reid immediately started making preparations and dispatched a messenger to order Lieutenant Campbell, who was camping in Mezoma village, to join him with 50 more men. This brought the tally of forces and weaponry at Captain Reid's disposal to "150 muskets, two three-pounders and a mortar, and about 800 friendly Nagas to fight on our side with their spears." These so-called 'friendly Nagas' belonged to surrounding villages which had by then pledged allegiance to the British. Not a few of these villages had previously suffered at the hands of Kikrüma, whose warriors had repeatedly raided them, killed and maimed several, or extracted heavy tribute. In a characteristic exercise of 'divide and

rule', British officer used their long-lingering antipathy and desire for revenge against Kikrūma to mould them into a strongly motivated fighting force. (Wouters, 2015)

Having assembled and readied his forces on the 9th February, Captain Reid guided them to the village of Kidima, situated about two miles from Kikrūma. From here they could see the village and saw Kikrūma warriors labouring hard to put in place impediments, barriers, and traps on the path leading to the village, which moreover looked so steep and difficult to scale that it made Captain Reid resolve to alter his strategy. Instead of approaching the village via the south end of the hill as initially planned, as well as anticipated by the villagers, he directed his troops about a mile north. This strategy of Captain Reid puzzled and worried the Kikrūma villagers. Their north gate was not as strongly fortified compared to the south entrance to the village, and with the troops already on their advance there was no time left to strengthen its northern defences. (Wouters, 2015)

He also heard that four other villages might join Kikrūma Naga, therefore, “the great caution was necessary” so he sent for Lt. Campbell who was still at Mezoma. Lt. Campbell along with 50 armed personnel while on their way to Saperhemah (Mao), mobilised 800 Naga warriors from those villages, earlier subdued by his Captain, to fight on their side. This was possible within such a short period, because, the Naga warriors of Kikrūma had taken many heads of the neighbouring villages in the past and these villages were awaiting an opportune time like this only to avenge their deaths. Having fully prepared; 150 personnel with muskets, two 3-pounder guns, one mortar, and 800 Naga allies with spears, Capt. Reid along with his reinforcements marched out from the “Saphemah village” (Pudunamai) on the 9th February, 1851, reached Kidima village, and encamped there on the 9th February, ‘about 2 miles from Kikrūma village, with Sidzö river in between’. (Achumi, 2012)

Meanwhile, the Kikrūma Naga warriors, from their village, took notice of the British troops and their Naga allies, marching closer to their village. They were getting ready to fight their enemy at the locations from the west end of their village facing Kidima, which gave them a great advantage. Because, the enemies were most likely expected to come from that direction, and if so, they had to climb steep hillocks to reach the village. Accordingly, boulders and logs were stockpiled on the edge of the hillocks to be pushed and rolled down at their enemies, as and when they climbed up from that direction. But Capt. Reid took notice from Kidima village, that the people of Kikrūma were busy in making impediments from that direction, so he decided not to attack from that point, and the next day, the 10th February, proceeded further North towards Kezoma village, ‘about two miles distant, and encamped near the river which runs at the foot of the Kikrūma mountain’. (Achumi, 2012)

The much-awaited and only expected entry point of their enemy did not take place and at one point in time the people of Kikrūma thought the Britishers were not coming, because they were seen marching

downward beyond Kezoma village, at the same time, they never expected their enemy would take on them from the northern end of their village. However, on the 11th February morning, British troops along with their Naga allies, ascended the mountain of the northern end of the village (Thivüputü) and headed towards Kikrüma for an inevitable battle that had awaited them. (Achumi, 2012)

The Bloodiest Battle of 1851:

This time the Kikrüma Naga warriors choose to fight their enemies from inside the village, in decidedly the middle of the village, because one of the two oracles of the village favoured that if not from the west end of the village as suggested by the first oracle, they should fight from within their village, so that they could win the battle. At the same time, they had not prepared or arranged any other means of fighting from any other direction, particularly from the northern direction, other than the West end of the village.

Meanwhile, in the presence of the British troops, the morale of the Naga allies was high, and in the process, they advanced much ahead of the main troops, entered the village, and got themselves engaged in fighting with the Kikrüma Naga Warriors. Then, many of the British Naga allies were killed. A Naga warrior Müswüri by name, had single-handedly killed scores of the allies of Britishers. Meanwhile, the greater number of Kikrüma Naga warriors positioned themselves behind the walls of the houses around the middle of the village after loosening the ropes of the wooden walls, so that if the enemies came near the walls, they be pushed down over their enemies and speared them. However, at the arrival of the main troops, and having secured a good position on a high piece of ground, commanding the village, (Rünitulü), the Britishers took notice of the tricks of their enemies and patiently waited till their enemies showed themselves in the open. As they came out, after a long wait, the Warriors of Kikrüma were taken by surprise by the 3-pounder guns, mortar and musketeers which they had never come across before. The guns were fired, which created the utmost unpleasant surprise; first time feeling the effect of the power of the guns, the warriors of Kikrüma fled in every direction in total confusion. (Achumi, 2012) The Kikrüma, thought brave were no match for the British forces which used modern firearms against their daos and spears. More than a hundred Kikrüma Nagas were killed including noted warriors against three killed and seventy wounded on the side of the enemy. Captain Reid saw the Kikrüma Native Braves turn out armed with spears and shields and fought a pitched battle with his sepoy and Naga allies. (Hutton, 1921)

The battle lasted the whole day, leaving more deaths on the side of Kikrüma Naga. The soldiers of the 1st and 2nd Assam light infantry drove out the Kikrüma Naga warriors from the village with great difficulty. Although Captain Reid had objected to burning the village, his Naga allies actuated by the feelings of revenge, set the village on fire from all sides, and a strong wind blowing at that time, the greater part of the village was burnt along with a huge quantity of grain, and only about six houses were saved in the centre of the village, in which the troops took shelter for the night.

Since the battle lasted that whole day, the troops and their allies had to spend the night in the village. So determined and brave were the Naga Warriors of Kikröma, throughout the night they kept their enemy attacked from all sides of the village and killed many of them in the darkness. In desperation, the Britishers had to fire blindly, the 3-pounder guns and mortar to scare away their enemies. The troops and its allies had suffered a miserable night without water, for the injured and the main troops. (Achumi, 2012) According to the oral history, the troops and its allies at one point in time tended to believe that, the Kikröma Naga had the command over the universe, because that night, the moon and the stars seemed to be standing still, making the night much longer than ever.

On February 12th 1851, the next morning, while the troops and its allies were retreating after having fought the bloodiest battle, through the south-west of the village gate, accidentally, they came to notice the presence of hundreds of old men, women and children in a secluded paddy field located outside the village where they had been kept, while their Warriors were fighting their enemies the previous day. The “ruthless barbarians allies” showed no mercy and once again actuated by the feeling of revenge for the many of their comrades killed on the previous day, “murdered and exterminated” the defenceless ‘young and old, women and children’. The troops had to forcibly stop their Naga allies from murdering the innocents. It is believed that the number of murders that took place on that fateful morning of 12th February was much higher than that of the previous day in the battle. According to the oral history of the village, dry leaves that lay in the nearby stream were washed away by the blood that flowed out of the ‘murder’ committed by the Naga allies. However, this ugly side of the battle had never been highlighted in any of the book or writing as expected, because, if so then the 19th-century history of the British in Naga Hills would have been altogether a different story. (Puroh, 2012)

In this way, the Britishers and its allies fought the “Bloodiest Battle ever fought in the North-East Frontier Hills,” on the 11th February 1851, at Kikröma village, leaving about 300 Kikröma warriors dead, many injured, and only two Naga allies killed and six wounded, and one camp-follower killed and one wound’. It is believed that the above loss on the side of the Britishers, particularly the Naga allies is far from the truth, and left a trail of bloodshed after having ‘murdered’ hundreds of innocent people; ‘women and children by the ‘ruthless barbarians allies’ on the 12th February 1851, ending the 10th and last military expedition in Naga Hills. (Puroh, 2012) Thus fell (the mighty) Kikröma, after one of the bloodiest battles ever fought in Assam (in those days Naga Hills was a part of Assam). (Wouters, 2015)

Consequences of the Battle of 1851:

The effects of the battle had caused much concern to the Britishers, consequently, in the month of March, 1851, the British Parliament adopted the policy of non-interference towards the Nagas, thus leaving them to decide their destiny.

After the successful expedition against the Kikrūma village, the Government realised the counter-productivity and expediency of the policy of taking excessive measures against a people whom they described as barbarians, savage and uncivilized. The effect of the battle had caused much concern to the Britishers, consequently, in the month of March of that year, the British Parliament adopted the Policy of Non-interference towards the Nagas, thus leaving them to decide their destiny. (Puroh, 2012) It was decided to try the combined effect of non-interference in their internal quarrels, of encouraging trade when they behaved well, and of shutting them out from the neighbouring markets when they gave trouble. With the close of this expedition, the Government decided upon a complete withdrawal from interference in the internal affairs of the Naga. Accordingly, the Governor General, Lord Dalhousie wrote his minutes of the 21st February 1851 as follows: (Achumi, 2012)

“Our future policy ought to be confined ourselves to our own frontier, to protect it, as it could and ought to be protected, never to meddle in fight and feuds of these savages, to encourage trade with them so long as they were peaceful towards us and rigidly to exclude them from all communication either to sell or to buy on this becoming turbulent or troublesome.”

Then, the British troops were eventually withdrawn from the Hill in March 1851 to Dimapur, the southern edge of the Naga Hills. Since then, the other incidents that took place in the Naga Hills during the British era were only in the form of ambushes, attacks, raids, punitive measures, etc. except the Second World War which was fought in and around Kohima, in the 20th century. (Puroh, 2012)

Conclusion:

Today, well over 160 years on, the story of the battle lives on amongst the Kikrūma villagers, who can't but feel awe at their forefathers' daring and determination to challenge the British Empire. It was a decision that cost them dearly. And yet, Kikrūma's challenge to the British remains a monumental act of resistance against colonial rule: a remarkable story of a single Naga village taking on the British Empire. It is a story that deserves to be remembered, shared much more widely, and indeed, given its rightful place in the history of colonial resistance. According to Kūhūpoyo Puro, a former Associate Professor of Kohima College who has long worked locally to preserve the tale of the battle of Kikrūma says: (Puroh, 2012)

“In the real sense of history, battlefield or war, the only incident worthy to be considered and called a Battlefield in the 19th century between the Britishers and the Nagas is the Battle of Kikrūma. Such is the importance of this battle, but it has never been highlighted as it should have been by the Historians as well as the Governments, both Centre and State.”

In commemoration of the fierce battle of 1851 fought between Kikrūma village and the British, the Kikrūma Village Council (KVC) has erected a monolith at Rūnyitu (battlefield zone) under Kikrūma village. According to KVC, retired secretary to the Government of Nagaland, Sachopra Vero dedicated the monolith on May 4, 2022, by unveiling the plaque which read as follows: (Morung Express, 2022)

“In memory of the battle of 1851 – The bloodiest battle ever fought in the North Eastern Frontier Hills between the British Imperial Army led by Captain Reid, Lt. Vincent and Lt. Campbell of the 1st and 2nd Assam Light Infantry, along with 800 Naga allies, and the warriors of Kikrūma village on 11th and 12th February 1851.”

Vero in his dedicatory message stated that the monolith would serve as a constant reminder for the present generation of Kikrūma village, the great values that the ancestors of the village cultivated and practised – values such as bravery, courage, valour, and above all, unity among its people. The event marked a historic day for the people of Kikrūma as they came together to honour the common future based on those admirable values handed down to the present generation.

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